

Location of the seal colonies investigated by the SEALS project (English Channel-Iroise sea area)

From East to West : Baie de Somme, Baie de Seine, Baie des Veys and Molène archipelago (noted *Iroise*)
Grey seals are shown in blue
 Harbour seals are shown in green
 Numbers indicate the number of seal individuals per colony

Spatial distribution analysis – Overview of available samples

Table 1. Number of individuals and type of samples available per species and colony.

These samples are biopsies collected during adult seal catch surveys conducted in France between 2019 and 2025, for both harbour seals (*Phoca vitulina*) and grey seals (*Halichoerus grypus*)

Colonies / species	n	Number of females/males	Blood	Skin	Whiskers	Blubber	Blubber + RNA later
		♀/♂	Stress biomarkers + PFAS	Mercury	SIA*	Organohalogenes + PFAS	Omics
Somme bay (2019-2024)	62						
Grey seal	23	3 /20	23	23	23	22	6
Harbour seal	39	3/ 39	39	39	39	39	14
Veys bay (2020-2024)	28						
Harbour seal	28	0/28	28	28	28	14	14
Seine bay (2022-2025)	17						
Grey seal	17	2/15	17	17	17	17	17
Molène archipelago (2024)	25						
Grey seal	25	11/14	25	25	25	25	25
Total	132		132	132	132	117	76

* Stable Isotope Analysis

Time trend analysis – Overview of available samples

Table 2. Number (n) of harbour seal (*Phoca vitulina*) pups stranded around the Bay of Somme, separated per time period. These animals were necropsied, and samples of their blubber and internal organs are available for analysis.

Year period	n
2009 - 2013	3
2014 - 2019	14
2020 - 2024	31
Total	48

Table 3. Number (n) of grey seals (*Halichoerus grypus*) pups stranded around the Molene archipelago, per time period. These animals were necropsied, and samples of their blubber and internal organs are available for analysis.

Year period	n
2008 - 2013	4
2014 - 2019	20
2020 - 2024	20
Total	44